

UMERC+OREC 2025 Conference

12-14 August | Corvallis, OR USA

Scaling Down a Wave Energy Converter to Match the Wave Spectrum of the North Carolina Coast

Mert Gursel¹, Rob Miller², Bora Karayaka^{1*}, Anderson de Queiroz², Mo Gabr², Yi-Hsiang Yu³

¹Western Carolina University, Cullowhee, NC 28723, United States of America

²North Carolina State University, Raleigh, NC 27695, United States of America

³National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University, No. 155, Sec. 2, Linong Street, Beitou District, Taipei City 112, Taiwan

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

This study investigates the scaling of a Wave Energy Converter (WEC) to match the wave spectrum of the North Carolina coast, with the goal of enhancing energy production efficiency and reducing the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE). A detailed wave resource assessment was conducted across 491 sea sites. The analysis included the development of joint probability distribution matrices, seasonal wave energy trends, and flux density mapping. A WEC model based on the Department of Energy's Reference Model 3 (RM3), modified with a slider-crank mechanism, was developed in WEC-Sim and fine-tuned using a reactive control algorithm. Site selection was informed by mechanical power outputs across various scaling scenarios. Final energy production and LCOE calculations were carried out using the System Advisor Model (SAM). The results indicated that the half-scale WEC configuration achieved the lowest LCOE. Although the LCOE remains relatively high, the study highlights the potential for improved project economics through co-location with offshore wind energy. Overall, the findings support the feasibility of scalable WEC deployment along the North Carolina coast and contribute to advancing sustainable offshore energy solutions.

Keywords: Wave Energy Converter (WEC) Scaling; Joint Probability Distribution; Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE); System Advisor Model (SAM); Slider-Crank Mechanism.

Introduction

Wave energy is recognized globally as a promising renewable energy source, offering vast untapped potential across the world's oceans. However, the successful deployment of Wave Energy Converters (WECs) depends heavily on adapting each system to the specific wave characteristics of its deployment region to ensure optimal performance and economic viability. Recent research efforts have increasingly explored the application of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques to improve wave energy forecasting and optimize WEC operation. These data-driven approaches have demonstrated significant potential in enhancing power output prediction, refining real-time control strategies, and optimizing component design by leveraging large-scale oceanographic datasets [1]. Also, studies have shown that DL models can provide accurate power output estimations in complex marine environments [2]. In addition to algorithmic advancements, foundational design efforts such as the U.S. Department of Energy's

Reference Model Project have established open-source benchmarks—like Reference Models 5 and 6—that support performance evaluation, cost analysis, and levelized cost of energy (LCOE) calculations, providing a standardized framework for assessing marine energy technologies [3-4]. Moreover, recent studies show that integrating offshore wind, wave, and current systems can reduce energy variability and enhance economic viability along the North Carolina coast [5].

In contrast to studies focused on algorithm development, the study presented in this paper is grounded in real-world oceanographic data specific to the southeastern U.S. coastline. Historical wave conditions extracted from WaveWatch III and HYCOM datasets spanning from July 2005 to December 2018, along the North Carolina coast with depths less than 200 meters are utilized. This dataset enabled a comprehensive wave resource assessment, including joint probability distribution (JPD) matrices, seasonal wave energy trends, and energy flux density mapping, which informed our WEC design optimization and site selection process.

This study distinguishes itself by targeting the relatively underexplored North Carolina coastline, where wave conditions differ significantly from those in traditionally studied high-energy locations. We present a systematic scaling methodology to adapt an established WEC design to this moderate-energy environment, with the goal of enhancing energy production efficiency while maintaining economic feasibility. By integrating regional wave statistics and applying scale-specific power limitations, the study not only aims to minimize the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) but also addresses practical constraints such as WEC scaling and varying array configurations. These efforts are followed by detailed cost assessments to evaluate capital requirements, energy yield, and overall project viability.

To the best of authors' knowledge, no comprehensive study to date has evaluated the LCOE of RM3-based WEC systems along the North Carolina coast while simultaneously exploring multiple device scales and array sizes. This research fills that gap by offering a tailored, region-specific framework that supports the broader goal of advancing wave energy deployment in a diverse range of coastal settings—particularly in areas where traditional full-scale deployments may not yet be economically justified.

The WEC model used in this study is based on the U.S. Department of Energy's Reference Model 3 (RM3), modified to incorporate a slider-crank mechanism that transforms vertical heave motion into continuous rotational energy. Simulations were carried out using WEC-Sim, employing a reactive control strategy to maximize energy extraction across a range of sea states. Site selection for deployment was based on mechanical power output across three distinct scaling scenarios: full-scale, half-scale, and one-third-scale device designs.

Methodology

This study followed a structured approach comprising three main phases: wave resource assessment, WEC model development and scaling, and energy production and economic analysis. Each phase was carefully designed to match the scaled WEC system with the wave characteristics of the North Carolina coast while aiming to optimize energy capture and reduce the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE).

1.1 Wave Resource Assessment

A comprehensive wave resource assessment was performed using historical oceanographic datasets. WaveWatch III model outputs provided significant wave height (H_s) and wave peak period (T_p) values, while water depth information was sourced from the HYCOM database.

The dataset was segmented into three-hour intervals to capture short-term variability in sea states. Statistical analyses included generating joint probability distribution (JPD) matrices to quantify the frequency of different combinations of H_s and T_p , along with seasonal trend analyses to capture temporal variations in wave energy availability. Energy flux density maps and standard deviation analyses were also developed to evaluate the spatial distribution and variability of the wave resource along the North Carolina coast.

To identify the most promising deployment locations, the performance of the WEC was evaluated across all 491 sea sites. The top 12 sites were selected based on the highest weighted average mechanical power outputs, incorporating the effects of mooring forces to ensure realistic performance estimation under operational conditions. While each scaling configuration individually considered ten selected sites, variations between full-scale, half-scale, and one-third-scale designs led to a total of twelve unique sea site locations across all configurations. These sites represent the geographical areas with the most favorable wave energy characteristics for efficient WEC deployment. Mechanical power outputs, including mooring effects, for the top-performing deployment sites are summarized in Table 1. Additionally, Figure 1 illustrates some of the top 12 optimal WEC deployment locations across all scales

along the North Carolina coast, highlighting regions with the highest energy potential. To further support site-specific analysis, Table 2 presents a representative Joint Probability Distribution (JPD) table for one of the best-performing sea sites. This JPD includes wave height and period distributions, with wave energy period T_e adjusted as required for compatibility with the System Advisor Model (SAM) tool [6].

Fig 1. Optimal Deployment Sites for the WEC Along the North Carolina Coast.

Table 1. Mechanical Power Outputs with Mooring for the Common Top 7 Sea Sites Across Different Scales

Latitude/ Longitude	1/1 Scale Power Output-Mooring (kW)	1/2 Scale Power Output-Mooring (kW)	1/3 Scale Power Output-Mooring (kW)	Capture Width Ratio (1x1 / 1x2 / 1x3)
35.3/-75.0	124.95	48.20	18.45	0.57 / 0.44 / 0.25
35.6/-74.8	124.33	47.82	18.30	0.57 / 0.44 / 0.25
35.2/-75.1	124.08	47.95	18.38	0.57 / 0.44 / 0.25
35.0/-75.3	123.91	47.28	18.14	0.57 / 0.44 / 0.25
35.1/-75.2	123.63	47.63	18.26	0.57 / 0.44 / 0.25
35.1/-75.1	123.30	47.75	18.32	0.57 / 0.44 / 0.25
35.5/-74.9	121.67	46.99	18.12	0.57 / 0.44 / 0.25

Table 2. Joint Probability Distribution (JPD) at Site 35.6°N, 74.8°W

Hs/Te	3.88	4.74	5.6	6.47	7.33	8.19	9.05	9.91
0.25	0.041	0.058	0.028	0.099	0.206	0.165	0.094	0.044
0.75	1.354	2.812	2.297	2.16	4.996	3.53	1.546	0.682
1.25	4.463	5.712	6.072	4.014	4.741	3.75	1.901	0.988
1.75	0.85	5.109	4.49	3.222	2.399	1.92	1.497	0.762
2.25	0.039	1.238	3.546	2.633	1.714	0.913	0.713	0.41
2.75	0	0.14	1.406	1.722	1.249	0.795	0.454	0.242
3.25	0	0.019	0.245	0.773	0.704	0.608	0.283	0.173
3.75	0	0	0	0.237	0.366	0.294	0.193	0.132
4.25	0	0	0	0.03	0.162	0.193	0.171	0.052

1.2 WEC Model Development and Scaling

The WEC model used in this study was based on the Department of Energy’s Reference Model 3 (RM3) with slider-crank mechanism, as illustrated in Figure 2. This design transforms vertical heave motion into continuous unidirectional rotational energy, offering more efficient mechanical-to-electrical energy conversion compared to conventional heaving buoy systems.

Simulations of WEC performance under various sea states were conducted using WEC-Sim, with a reactive control algorithm implemented to synchronize float velocity with the wave excitation force, enhancing energy capture efficiency. Scaling analyses were performed for three WEC sizes: full-scale, half-scale, and one-third-scale configurations.

To assess performance under practical constraints, maximum power output limits were applied across all Wave Energy Converter (WEC) scales. For the full-scale system, the maximum electrical power output recorded was 1,095 kW, with thresholds of 858 kW, 572 kW, and 286 kW imposed to simulate generator or Power Take Off (PTO) system limitations. Similarly, for the half-scale design, which peaked at 127 kW, output caps of 63 kW and 32 kW were applied. The one-third-scale system reached a maximum of 34 kW, output caps of 17 kW and 8.5 kW were applied. Power values exceeding each threshold were capped, while lower values remained unchanged. This standardized capping strategy enabled consistent evaluation of energy production impacts and supported fair cost-per-watt comparisons across different WEC scales.

In addition to individual device scaling, array configurations were examined to assess the impact of deployment size on capital costs and energy production. To maintain comparable overall power ratings across different scales, the number of devices in each array was adjusted proportionally based on the rated capacity of each unit. For the half-scale WEC, two array sizes were modeled: a 10×10 array consisting of 100 WECs and a larger 15×18 array totaling 270 WECs. Structural assembly costs were scaled by factors of one-half and one-quarter of the full-scale system costs for the smaller and larger arrays, respectively. Similarly, for the one-third-scale WEC design, arrays of 100 WECs (10×10 layout) and 650 WECs (25×26 layout) were analyzed, with structural costs reduced to one-third and one-ninth of the full-scale reference value. These different array configurations enabled a comprehensive evaluation of how device scaling and deployment size influence the overall economic feasibility of wave energy converter systems.

Fig 2. WEC Model Block Diagram

1.3 Energy Production and Economic Analysis

SAM was employed to conduct annual energy production simulations and to calculate the LCOE for each WEC design and deployment scenario. SAM integrated electrical power output data from WEC-Sim with detailed performance modeling, financial assumptions, and cost structures relevant to wave energy systems.

Results

Final energy production estimates and economic assessments were conducted using SAM, which provided annual energy output calculations and LCOE evaluations. The results identified that the half-scale WEC configuration achieved the lowest LCOE among the evaluated designs. Although the calculated LCOE remains relatively high, the study highlights the potential for cost improvements through the co-location of wave energy systems with offshore wind farms.

Overall, this study demonstrates the feasibility of scaling WEC designs to match the wave spectrum of the North Carolina coast, contributing to the advancement of integrated and sustainable offshore renewable energy solutions.

The results from the WEC-Sim simulations and SAM analyses provide insights into the performance and economic viability of the scaled WEC designs. The analysis presented below focuses on five common deployment sites that

were evaluated across all three WEC scales to ensure a consistent comparison of energy output and cost-effectiveness. Initially, the full-scale RM3 heaving buoy (benchmark WEC) was compared to the full-scale slider-crank WEC design. As illustrated in Figure 3, the slider-crank configuration achieved 45.3% higher capacity factor and 29.8% lower LCOE compared to the traditional heaving buoy design. The mechanical efficiency improvements introduced by the slider-crank mechanism led to enhanced energy conversion, supporting its selection for further scaling investigations.

The study subsequently examined the impact of scaling on WEC performance. Figure 4 illustrates the results for full-scale, half-scale, and one-third-scale slider-crank configurations. Among the three, the half-scale WEC consistently delivered the best balance of cost and performance, achieving the lowest Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) at 58.7 ¢/kWh and a capacity factor of 47.9%. The one-third-scale design exhibited the highest capacity factor at 63.7%, but with a higher LCOE of 79.6 ¢/kWh. In contrast, the full-scale configuration showed the lowest capacity factor of 19.9% and the highest LCOE at 111.6 ¢/kWh.

Another key comparison in this study involves evaluating different array configurations for scaled WEC systems. The half-scale WEC was analyzed using both 10×10 and 15×18 arrays, while the one-third-scale WEC was assessed with 10×10 and 25×26 arrays. The 15×18 configuration for the half-scale design resulted in a 12.3% decrease in LCOE, and the 25×26 configuration for the one-third-scale design led to a 32% reduction in LCOE. In both cases, the capacity factor remained nearly unchanged.

Figure 3. LCOE (left) and Capacity Factor (right) at Full Scale: Comparison between the Benchmark RM3-WEC and the Slider Crank WEC

Figure 4. LCOE (left) and Capacity Factor (right): Comparison Across Different Scales and Power Ratings for the Slider Crank WEC

Conclusion

Overall, the analysis confirmed that careful scaling of WEC designs, matched to local wave conditions, is essential for maximizing energy production and minimizing LCOE. The half-scale slider-crank WEC emerged as the most promising candidate for deployment along the North Carolina coast. Although the calculated LCOE values remain higher than those of conventional renewable technologies, co-location with offshore wind farms could significantly improve the economic competitiveness of wave energy projects by leveraging shared infrastructure and operational resources.

References

- [1] A. Shadmani, M. R. Nikoo, A. H. Gandomi, R.-Q. Wang, and B. Golparvar, "A review of machine learning and deep learning applications in wave energy forecasting and WEC optimization," *Energy Strategy Reviews*, vol. 50, Sep. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17010128>
- [2] O. M. Gursel, P. Yanik, and H. B. Karayaka, "Integration of Machine Learning for Enhanced Wave Energy Converter Power Output Estimation," *Proc. North American Power Symposium (NAPS)*, Nov. 2024. doi:10.1109/NAPS61145.2024.10741837
- [3] D. L. Bull, C. Smith, D. S. Jenne, P. Jacob, A. Copping, S. Willits, A. Fontaine, D. Brefort, M. E. Gordon, R. Copeland, and R. A. Jepsen, *Reference Model 6 (RM6): Oscillating Wave Energy Converter*, Technical Report, U.S. Department of Energy, Oct. 2014. Accessed May 2, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1159445>. doi: 10.2172/1159445
- [4] Y. H. Yu, D. S. Jenne, R. Thresher, A. Copping, S. Geerlofs, and L. A. Hanna, *Reference Model 5 (RM5): Oscillating Surge Wave Energy Converter*, Technical Report, U.S. Department of Energy, Jan. 2015. Accessed May 2, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1169778>. doi: 10.2172/1169778
- [5] V. A. D. de Faria, A. R. de Queiroz, and J. F. DeCarolis, "Optimizing offshore renewable portfolios under resource variability," *Applied Energy*, vol. 330, p. 120012, Sept. 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.120012
- [6] System Advisor Model™ Version 2024.12.12 (SAM™ 2024.12.12), National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Golden, CO. Accessed May 2, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://sam.nrel.gov/download/version-2024-12-12.html>